

THE STRUCTURE OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The article substantiates the relevance of the integrative approach and its functions, presents the components of the structure of the integrative approach. The aspects, functions, principles and objectives of an integrative approach to learning a foreign language are highlighted. Also, the author describes methods that can be used when learning a foreign language on the basis of integrative approach. One of the most important trends in the development of higher education in the XXI century is the intensification of integration processes at all levels, from personal to interstate.*

Keywords: *integrative approach, learning a foreign language, methods of teaching a foreign language. the components of the structure of the integrative approach.*

At the moment, changes are taking place in the Uzbek education system: it becomes focused on entering the world educational space. One of the most important trends in the development of higher education in the XXI century is the intensification of integration processes at all levels, from personal to interstate. Integration is one of the most significant innovative phenomena in education today. It surpasses all other phenomena "in breadth of experimental embodiment, depth of creative conception, duration and dialectic of historical development" [2, p. 26].

The main function of integration processes is to achieve a synergetic effect based on cooperation and cooperation, which prevail over differentiation and isolation. Integration processes lead to the formation of new elements, changing, transforming the current ones into more effective ones. The processes of globalization, changes in all spheres of human activity are changing the requirements for higher professional education.

The education system must meet the new requirements of society. As a rule, the teacher teaches only his subject, isolated from all others. But this approach does not form a set of knowledge that students must master for successful professional activity. Therefore, new approaches in training are needed. Scientists have confirmed the need to create fundamental pedagogical structures, the task of which will be the formation of a common culture of students, preparation for successful professional activity and the development of a holistic worldview. The integrative approach, formed in the domestic and foreign methodology, seems to be the most productive and effective in this regard. It can solve the problem of holistic training of future specialists thanks not only to the integration of disciplines, but also to the merging of methods, forms and organization of the educational process.

As V.F. Tenishcheva rightly notes, "integration ensures the movement of the pedagogical system towards its greater integrity and, as a result, leads to an increase in the level of the educational process, which is expressed in the formation of the necessary competencies competencies of students" [3, p. 69]. According to I.A. Zimnaya and E.V. Zemtsova, the integrative approach is "a holistic representation of a set of objects, phenomena, processes united

by the commonality of at least one of the characteristics, as a result of which its new quality is created" [1, p. 14-19].

So, let's consider the structure of an integrative approach to teaching a foreign language. It includes aspects, principles, goals and results. Let's consider the components of the integrative approach: methodical, organizational-activity and informative. And understanding themselves, knowing their needs, students strive even more for self-development.

The organizational and activity component involves the integration of learning forms of various subjects, which will facilitate the use of more creative tasks aimed at the formation of creativity and the destruction of stereotypes of students. The content component includes educational activities (using the methods described above, qualitative selection of material that contributes to achieving the goals of the integrative course) and extracurricular activities (intercultural interaction, independent study of the material).

The following basic principles of an integrative approach in teaching a foreign language can be distinguished:

- the principle of cultural conformity;
- the principle of creativity;
- the principle of orientation to self-development and self-education;
- the principle of variability;
- the principle of multicultural self-determination and self-actualization of the individual;
- the principle of tolerance;
- the principle of the dialogue of cultures.

Among the main goals of the integrative approach in teaching a foreign language, it seems important to highlight the following:

- formation of a holistic picture of the world (students understand the purpose of studying subjects more deeply, realizing the connection between them, thus increasing motivation for the learning process);
- formation of new skills and abilities due to the interpenetration and mutual enrichment of the system with elements of various systems (thanks to this, the possibilities of students are expanded);
- the formation of a new type of personality, free from stereotypes and free to choose actions, which is important in connection with the formation of a personality ready for constructive intercultural communication;
- the formation of a tolerant personality, which at this stage of the development of society is one of the priorities of the educational system;
- the formation (by creating problematic situations) of a creative personality ready to find solutions in non-standard situations;
- formation of moral values of students (inclusion of moral material); formation of key competencies (communicative, socio-cultural, educational and cognitive).

The result of the integrative approach in teaching a foreign language is: the intensification of the learning process, the systematization of educational and cognitive activities, the formation of key competencies, the formation of a personality ready for effective intercultural communication, the formation of professional students' skills, comprehensive personality development, the formation of variability of thinking, the formation of a new type of personality of the student.

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